

Rac-4k

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-174-RAC-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	45	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 174 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/31/2021 3:04:35 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/22/2022 10:58:02 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.105	1682765	49.90	137953
2	9.728	1689325	50.10	91127

Asy-4k

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-175-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	55	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 175 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/31/2021 3:25:54 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/22/2022 11:01:38 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.100	5234480	90.27	429416
2	9.715	564523	9.73	31002